

Condensation of Chloral and Bromal Hydrates with Amides.

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In extension of a study of the condensation of chloral with amides by Meldrum and Bhojraj (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1926, p. 146) the authors have prepared a number of chloral and bromalamides and have examined their chemical properties.

Chloralacetamide was prepared by Pinner (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1963) by the action of ammonia on chloralacetyl chloride and by Schiff and Tassinari (*ibid.*, p. 168) from chloralammonia and acetyl chloride. Jacobson (*Annalen*, 1871, 157, 245) prepared chloralacetamide and chloralbenzamide from chloral and respective amides. The authors have prepared chloralamides and bromalamides by heating an equimolecular mixture of chloral or bromal hydrate and amides till a solid was obtained. Dichloralmalonamide and dichloralsuccinamide were obtained by heating under reflux a mixture of the finely powdered amide with chloral. Dichloralmalonamide formed a paste which set to a glassy mass which on keeping in water for several days gave a solid. Bromalsalicylamide and bromal-*o*-methoxybenzamide also formed pastes solidifying on treatment with water.

The anhydro derivatives of chloralamides were first obtained by Moscheles (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1803) by the action of acetic anhydride in cold sodium hydroxide solution. Moscheles (*loc. cit.*), Hantzsch (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1248), Diels and Seib (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4062) and Diels and Gukassianz (*Ber.*, 1910, 43, 3314) gave the anhydro derivatives the constitution $R \cdot CO \cdot N : CH \cdot CCl_3$. Feist (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 945) showed that the products have the constitution $(R \cdot CO \cdot NH \cdot CH \cdot CCl_3)_2O$. It has been found by the authors that one molecule of chloralsalicylamide loses one molecule of water to form an anhydro derivative while other chloralamides and bromalamides lose water in the way that Feist observed, two molecules lose one molecule of water and form an anhydro derivative.

Previous workers using acetyl chloride in presence of sodium hydroxide solution obtained the anhydro derivatives while the acetyl derivatives were obtained, if at all, as a by-product. The authors prepared

the acetyl derivatives (i) by dissolving the chloral or bromalamides in pyridine and adding acetyl chloride, (ii) by the action of acetic anhydride containing sulphuric acid. Chloralsalicylamide gave by both the methods the anhydro compound which absorbed bromine. It gave the acetyl derivative by keeping it with acetic anhydride and sulphuric acid for a few days. Diacetylchloralsalicylamide was obtained by heating chloralsalicylamide with acetic anhydride in presence of sulphuric acid. Bromal-*o*-methoxybenzamide gave with acetic anhydride in sodium hydroxide solution a mixture of the acetyl and the anhydro derivatives from which the components were separated by fractional crystallisation from ethyl acetate.

The methyl ethers were obtained from the chloral or bromalamides with dimethyl sulphate in presence of dilute sodium hydroxide solution (*cf.* Feist, *loc. cit.*).

The reduction products were obtained by stirring the chloral and bromalamides with acetic acid and zinc dust. In the case of chloral-*p*-toluamide the reduction mixture was kept in hot water while in the case of bromalsalicylamide and bromal-*o*-methoxybenzamide the temperature was not allowed to rise above 37°. In the case of other bromalamides the reduction mixture was kept at 15°. The group CH(OH)·CCl_3 is changed on reduction to CH:CCl_2 and the group CH(OH)·CBr_3 to CH:CBr_2 or CH:CHBr as shown by Yelburgi and Wheeler (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 217). The compounds prepared are summarised in the following Tables.

TABLE I.

Name.	Formula.	Appearance.	M. p.	Analysis.	
				Found.	Calc.
Dichloral malonamide	$C_7H_8O_4N_2Cl_6$	Plates	171	Cl 53.6 %	53.6 %
Dichloral succinamide	$C_8H_{10}O_4N_2Cl_6$	Plates	172	51.7	51.8
Benzoyl chloralacetamide	$C_{11}H_{10}O_3NCl_3$	Long plates	101.02	34.1	34.3
Acetyl chloral- <i>n</i> -butyramide	$C_8H_{12}O_3NCl_3$	Needles	84.86	38.6	38.5
Benzoyl chloral- <i>n</i> -butyramide	$C_{13}H_{14}O_3NCl_3$	Needles	126.27	31.2	31.5
Methyl chloral- <i>n</i> -butyramide	$C_7H_{12}O_2NCl_3$	Needles	94.95	42.9	42.8
Anhydro chloral- <i>n</i> -butyramide	$C_{12}H_{18}O_3N_2Cl_6$	Needles	173.74	47.1	47.2
Acetyl chloral benzamide	$C_{11}H_{10}O_3NCl_3$	Needles	153.54	34.3	34.3
Chloral- <i>p</i> -toluamide	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2NCl_3$	Hexagonal plates	152	37.5	37.7
β -Dichloroethylene- <i>p</i> -toluamide	$C_{10}H_9ONCl_2$	Long plates	101	30.5	30.8
Acetyl chloral phenylacetamide	$C_{12}H_{12}O_3NCl_3$	Needles	152	32.9	32.8
Benzoyl chloral phenylacetamide	$C_{17}H_{14}O_3NCl_3$	Needles	164	27.6	27.5
Diacetyl chloral salicylamide	$C_{13}H_{13}O_5NCl_3$	Needles	134	28.8	28.9
Anhydro chloral salicylamide	$C_9H_6O_2NCl_3$	Long plates	174.75	39.9	39.9
Acetyl anhydro chloral salicylamide	$C_{11}H_8O_3NCl_3$	Plates	53.55	34.3	34.5

TABLE II.

Name.	Formula.	Appearance.	M. p.	Analysis.	
				Found. Br, 62.3 %	Calc. 62.5 %
Acetylbromalacetamide	$C_6H_8O_3NBr_3$	Square plates	120	57.7	57.8
Bromal- <i>n</i> -butyramide	$C_6H_{10}O_2NBr_3$	Rhombic plates	145	57.7	57.8
Bromalbenzamide	$C_9H_8O_2NBr_3$	Rhombic plates	148	59.6	59.7
Acetylbromalbenzamide	$C_{11}H_{10}O_3NBr_3$	Needles	142	54.1	54.0
Benzoylbromalbenzamide	$C_{16}H_{12}O_3NBr_3$	Needles	164-65	47.8	47.4
Methylbromalbenzamide	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2NBr_3$	Needles	140-41	57.7	57.8
Anhydrobromalbenzamide	$C_{18}H_{14}O_3N_2Br_3$	Plates	199 (decomp.)	61.0	60.9
β -Bromoethylenebenzamide	C_9H_8ONBr	Needles	122-23	35.2	35.4
Bromal- <i>p</i> -toluamide	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2NBr_3$	Hexagonal plates	151	57.4	57.7
β -Bromoethylene- <i>p</i> -toluamide	$C_{10}H_{10}ONBr$	Long plates	128-29	33.2	33.3
Bromalphenylacetamide	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2NBr_3$	Rhombic plates	146	57.7	57.8
Acetylbromalphenylacetamide	$C_{12}H_{12}O_3NBr_3$	Tiny needles	151	52.2	52.4
Benzoylbromalphenylacetamide	$C_{17}H_{14}O_3NBr_3$	Needles	143	46.3	46.1
Methylbromalphenylacetamide	$C_{11}H_{12}O_2NBr_3$	Long plates	127-28	55.8	55.8
Anhydrobromalphenylacetamide	$C_{20}H_{18}O_3N_2Br_6$	Long plates	150	58.9	58.9
β -Bromoethylenephénylacetamide	$C_{10}H_{10}ONBr$	Needles	115-16	33.3	33.3
Bromalsalicylamide	$C_9H_8O_3NBr_3$	Cubes	161	57.3	57.4
β -Dibromoethylenesalicylamide	$C_9H_7O_2NBr_2$	Feathery plates	177	49.3	49.8

TABLE II. (contd.)

Name.	Formula.	Appearance.	M. p.	Analysis.	
				Found. Br, 55.5 %	Calc. 55.6 %
Bromal- <i>o</i> -methoxybenzamide	$C_{10}H_{10}O_3NBr_3$	Cubes or plates	141-42	55.5	55.6
Acetyl bromal- <i>o</i> -methoxybenzamide	$C_{12}H_{12}O_4NBr_3$	Square plates	115-17	50.6	50.6
Methyl bromal- <i>o</i> -methoxybenzamide	$C_{11}H_{12}O_3NBr_3$	Long plates	103-04	53.7	53.8
Anhydro bromal- <i>o</i> -methoxybenzamide	$C_{20}H_{18}O_5N_2Br_6$	Needles	185-86	56.8	56.7
β -Bromoethylene- <i>o</i> -methoxybenzamide	$C_{10}H_9O_2NBr_2$	Needles	128	47.3	47.7

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